

Simultaneous Determination of Rhodium(III) and Palladium(II) using Bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone as a Sensitive as well as Selective Complexing Agent

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The analytical applications of a few thiocarbohydrazones have been investigated¹. The present paper reports the results of the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and rhodium(III) using bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BTA-TCH) as a chelating agent.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes revealed that the maximum absorption of these complexes was 390 nm. The absorption values of the reagent blanks were appreciably low at this region.

The optimum range of pH for complex formation and quantitative extraction of the Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes were respectively 2.2–5.0 and 4.8–5.9. Prior to extraction the Rh^{III} complex had to be heated. Both the complexes are yellow in colour and quite stable and showed no appreciable change even after 24 h.

The empirical formulae of the complexes were determined by the mole-ratio method² and verified by the conventional slope-ratio method³. The compositions of the Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes (reagent : metal) were found to be 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 respectively.

The results of single extraction of the Pd and Rh complexes using equal volumes of the solvent

and water (adjusted to the corresponding optimum pH values) at 30° are shown in Table 1.

Solvent	TABLE I			
	Palladium		Rhodium	
	D*	% E**	D*	% E**
Isobutyl methyl ketone	41.65	97.62	13.44	93.06
1,2-Dichloroethane	95.00	98.95	26.60	96.00
Chloroform	4.56	82.10	3.70	78.72
Benzene	0.7535	42.96	6.50	86.66
Carbontetrachloride	0.0130	1.28	7.59	88.35
Ethyl acetate	95.00	98.95	49.10	98.00

*D≡Distribution coefficient. **E≡Percentage extracted.

Beer's law was found to be obeyed for both the Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes at 390 nm over the concentration ranges 0.475–1.93 and 0.34–1.34 ppm respectively. Molar absorptivity of the complexes and the sensitivity of the colour reactions are recorded in Table 2. The relative mean error and the relative standard deviations obtained from six identical sets of experiments are also recorded.

For the Pd complex with 24 µg of the metal, the average of determinations was 24.15 µg which varied between 24.15 ± 0.1836 µg at 95% confidence limit. For the Rh complex with 15.56 µg of the metal, the average of determination was found to be 15.33 µg which varied between 15.33 ± 0.1338 µg at 95% confidence limit.

NOTES

TABLE 2

Compd.	Molar absorp. $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^4$	Sandell's sensitivity* $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$	Relative mean error	Standard deviation %	Coefficient of variation %
Pd-complex	4.5	0.002 3	0.604 5	0.175 0	0.724 6
Rh-complex	6.0	0.001 7	0.650 0	0.127 0	0.820 0

*Ref. 4.

The results of tolerance limits (i.e. concentration of the diverse ions causing an error less than $\pm 2\%$ in the transmittance value) are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Foreign ion added	Amount tolerated (mg) in 24 μg Pd	Amount tolerated (mg) in 15.56 μg Rh
Ti ^{IV}	1.0	1.0 ^b
V ^V	1.75	1.0
Cr ^{III}	1.0	1.0 ^b
Mn ^{II}	1.0	1.0
Fe ^{III}	1.5 ^a	1.0 ^b
Co ^{III}	2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b
Ni ^{II}	1.7	2.0
Cu ^{II}	0.5 ^a	0.5 ^b
Zn ^{II}	2.0	2.0
Cd ^{II}	2.0	2.0
Hg ^{II}	0.3 ^a	0.5 ^b
Pb ^{II}	1.5	1.0
Bi ^{III}	1	1.5
Au ^{III}	1.0 ^b	0.11 ^b
Mn ^{VI}	1.0	1.2
W ^{VI}	1.6	1.5
U ^{VI}	1.5	1.0
Os ^{VI}	0.15 ^d	0.38 ^b
Pd ^{II}	—	0.12 ^b
Rh ^{III}	0.31	—
Ru ^{III}	0.16 ^e	0.11
Ir ^{III}	1.2	nil
Pt ^{IV}	0.25 ^d	0.23 ^d

^aIn presence of EDTA; ^bin presence of Ca-EDTA; ^cprior extraction; ^dreduced with sulphurous acid; ^ereduced with NH_4OH , HCl.

Determination of Pd and Rh in synthetic mixture: The results of estimation of Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} in synthetic mixture are shown in Table 4. Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} were also determined in a binary mixture of these two metals (Table 5).

TABLE 4—ESTIMATION OF Pd AND Rh IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

Synthetic solution	Meial ion found (μg)* with 95% confidence limit	Relative mean error %
Pd ^{II} (24 μg) + Ru ^{III} (108 μg) + Os ^{VI} (120 μg) + Pt ^{IV} (120 μg) + Ir ^{III} (200 μg) + Rh ^{III} (46.7 μg)	Pd ^{II} 23.85 $\pm$ 0.26	0.88
Rh ^{III} (31 μg) + Ru ^{III} (108 μg) + Pd ^{II} (48 μg) + Os ^{VI} (60 μg)	Rh ^{III} 31.18 $\pm$ 0.14	0.53

*With 95% confidence limit.

TABLE 5—ESTIMATION OF Pd AND Rh IN BINARY MIXTURES OF THE TWO

Amount present (μg)		Amount found (μg)	
Pd ^{II}	Rh ^{III}	Pd ^{II}	Rh ^{III}
24	31	23.75	31.3
48	15.56	47.5	15.7
72	15.56	72.32	15.0

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss PMQ-2 spectrophotometer was used. The pH was measured with a Systronic 331 instrument. Stock solutions of Pd and Rh were prepared by dissolving their chlorides (Johnson and Mathey) (1 g each) in dilute HCl and standardised respectively by gravimetric and hydrolytic precipitation⁶ methods. Solutions of Pd and Rh were prepared by dilution of the stock solution with distilled water. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared in distilled water or dilute HCl. Dilute HCl and 10% sodium acetate solution were employed to maintain the acidity of the solutions.

A 1×10^{-3} M bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BTATCH) solution was prepared in ethanol.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure: An aliquot containing known amount of Pd^{II} was diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and its pH was adjusted to 2.2–5.0. The reagent solution (1–2 ml) was then added and allowed to stand for 10–15 min. The solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 $\times$ 5 ml) and made up to 25 ml with ethyl acetate, then dried and the absorbance was measured at 390 nm against reagent blank.

In the case of Rh^{III} the pH was adjusted to 4.8–5.9 with HCl and 10% sodium acetate solution. After addition of the reagent solution, the mixture was heated over a boiling-water bath for 15–20 min. Subsequent extraction and absorbance measurements at 390 nm were same as those for Pd^{II}.

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